

Alliances questionnaire

Question	Options	Correct reply
Italy is part of at least an alliance.	True/False	True
Only universities in northern Italy joined alliances.	True/False	False
Alliances include only European countries.	True/False	False
How many alliances are there?	A. Less than 10 B. Between 10 and 25 C. Between 26 and 50 D. More than 50	D
How big are alliances?	A. Up to two B. Between 3 to 5 C. Between 6 and 10 D. Even more than 10	D
New alliances are formed every year.	True/False	True